

IMPROVING THE INSURANCE ACTIVITY CLASSIFIER TAKING INTO ACCOUNT ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

Jamolova Khonzoda Orolboy qizi

2nd year student of Tashkent State University
of Economics, Faculty of "Finance and Accounting"
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Abstract: Various reforms are being carried out for the development of insurance in our country. Including opinions and suggestions on expanding insurance by relying on foreign experience.

Key words: Insurance, life insurance, insurance companies, foreign experience, qualified personnel.

Introduction

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 27, 2002 No. 413 "On measures to further develop the insurance market". On the basis of this decision, adoption of the "Regulation on Licensing Insurance Activities of Insurers and Insurance Brokers" and "Classification of Insurance Activities". In it, the life insurance network consisted of 4 classes, and the general insurance network consisted of 17 classes. Ensuring the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5265 dated October 23, 2021 "On additional measures to digitize the insurance market and develop the life insurance sector" and in order to expand the classification of insurance activities and thereby popularize the types of insurance services in the life insurance industry and personal insurance market, develop insurance products that serve the needs of the population and the economy, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated June 9, 2022 Decision No. 323 "On making changes to some decisions of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as considering some of them as invalid" was adopted.

In particular, the field of life insurance includes V-class "Life insurance for the provision of obligations", VI-class "Long-term voluntary pension insurance" and VII-class "Life insurance with return of capital" If so, the 18th class "Medical insurance" was included in the field of general insurance.

In developed countries, insurance is much more developed, including the USA, Germany, Japan, and so on. When it comes to getting life insurance in Japan, 100% of people use life insurance services. We know that Japan is classified as a hotbed of earthquakes. Earthquakes occur more than 10 times a day. Injuries or more severe injuries can occur, and in this process, the public's social protection tool is insurance companies. Article 25 of the Japanese Constitution states that "All people have the right to maintain a minimum standard of healthy and civilized life" and "The State shall use its efforts to promote and expand social welfare and security." Patients can receive care from a provider of their choice. For example, a man working for a company in Tokyo may visit a specialist at a university hospital near his office on an outpatient basis during his free time, and be seen by a doctor at a clinic near his home in Kanagawa prefecture on the same weekend. According to the guidelines, referral letters are

required for outpatient visits at major hospitals; however, in most cases, patients can see specialists at larger hospitals as long as they are willing to pay a few thousand yen extra. Doctors also have freedom of practice. Additionally, if physicians hold a medical license, they are free to practice in any specialty, whether or not they hold specialty certifications. For example, a surgeon may practice as an "Internist/Orthopedic Surgeon" and it is not uncommon to see signs outside clinics listing multiple specialties.

There are different types of life insurance policies in Japan with different features and benefits, including term life, whole life, universal life, and variable life. More than 3,000 health insurance funds are divided into three insurance schemes: employer-based health insurance, residence-based National Health Insurance (NHI) and health insurance for persons over 75 years of age. schemes.

And in Germany, the lower the cost of claims, the lower the type class. Type classes reflect the damage and accident records of each registered vehicle model. The last three years are taken into account to calculate type classes, vehicle damage and resulting claim costs. The individual type class is always ranked relative to the market average. If relatively less damage was done and covered by the car type compared to previous years, the model is placed in a lower type class. It works the same way in reverse. The type class for each model is updated annually and is therefore not a static rating.

In motor vehicle liability insurance, the type class is primarily influenced by the type of vehicle and the driving style of the user. In comprehensive insurance, in addition to collisions, damages caused by car theft, car fires, glass damage or natural disasters are also taken into account when classifying the type class. There are 16 available types of classes (10-25) in motor vehicle owners' liability insurance, 25 (10-34) in comprehensive insurance, 24 (10-33) in partial coverage. Classification of types is not mandatory for insurance companies and can be applied immediately for new contracts and existing contracts.

Conclusion

In conclusion, since the efficiency of the development of the insurance market in Uzbekistan is very low, it will be necessary to take various measures for its development. In particular, the training of qualified personnel, improvement of laws, and reliance on foreign experience are considered to be one of the most important, and this is like treading the reliable path carelessly. The above-mentioned countries are clear examples of this and create a basis for the development of our insurance market.

References:

- 1.<https://www.ruv.de/kfz-versicherung/car-insurance-germany-quotes-calculator>
- 2.<https://japanhpn.org/en/section-3-1/>
- 3.https://tfi.uz/ru/news/Oquv_markaz_2023
- 4.Z. Iqbal, A. Mirakhor. "An Introduction to Islamic Finance". John Wiley & Sons (Asia) Pte. Ltd. Published in 2011

